

Development of simple and sensitive spectrophotometric method for the detection of Abacavir sulphate in bulk and dosage forms using Azocarmamine-G[†]

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Manuscript received online 16 August 2013, accepted 11 December 2013

Abstract : A simple and sensitive visible spectrophotometric method has been developed for assay of Abacavir sulphate (AVS), an antiviral agent, in bulk and dosage forms. It is based on the formation of ion-association complex involving the secondary amino group of Abacavir sulphate and the acidic dye Azocarmamine-G ($\lambda_{\max} = 540$) to form colored species. All the variables have been optimized and are validated statistically. Beer's law limits are found in the range of 50–150 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Recovery is in the range of 99.38 ± 0.87 to $99.97.2 \pm 0.92\%$. The proposed method is simple, economical and sensitive for the quantitative determination of Abacavir sulfate.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, Abacavir sulphate (antiviral agent), Azocarmamine-G (ACG), formulations.

Introduction

Abacavir sulphate (AVS) is a carbocyclic synthetic nucleoside analogue with inhibitory activity against HIV. The chemical name of Abacavir sulphate is : [(1*S*,4*R*)-4-[2-amino-6-(cyclopropylamino)-9*H*-purin-9-yl]-2-cyclopentene-1-methanol sulphate (salt) (2 : 1)] (Fig. 1). The drug is official in Martindale¹ and PDR². Few HPLC

and other methods reported in the literature for the assay of drug in pharmaceutical formulations³⁻⁹. But, relatively little attention has been paid in developing visible spectrophotometric methods¹⁰⁻¹⁸. The analytically important functional groups in the drug have not been exploited properly so far and hence there is a need to develop sensitive and flexible visible spectrophotometric method. Authors have made an attempt in this direction and succeeded in developing visible spectrophotometric method using Azocarmamine-G (ACG).

Experimental

Instrumentation :

The measurements were made on a SL-177 model (Elico, India) visible spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells and on a UNICAM UV 500 spectrophotometer (Thermo Electron Corporation, UK). All pH measurements were made using a LI 120 digital pH meter (Elico, India).

Fig. 1. Structure of Abacavir sulphate.

[†]Paper accepted for the Poster Session of International Conference on Global Trends in Pure and Applied Chemical Sciences (ICGTCS-2012) held at Udaipur (Rajasthan), India on 3-4 March, 2012.

Reagents :

All the reagents were of analytical grade and aqueous solutions of Azocarmamine-G (Loba; 0.05%, 5.50×10^{-4} M), buffer solution (pH 1.5), HCl (E. Merck; 0.1 M) and chloroform (Qualigens) for the proposed method were prepared in double distilled water.

Standard drug solution :

A 1 mg mL⁻¹ solution was freshly prepared by dissolving 100 mg of pure drug in 100 mL of distilled water and this stock solution was diluted stepwise with distilled water to obtain the working standard solution of, 500 µg mL⁻¹.

General procedure :

Into a series of 125.0 ml separating funnels containing aliquots of standard drug solution (1.0–3.0 ml, 500 µg/ml), 6.0 ml of buffer solution (pH 1.5) and 2.0 ml of 5.50×10^{-4} M dye solution were added. The total volume in each separating funnel was adjusted to 15.0 ml with distilled water. To each separating funnel 10.0 ml of chloroform was added and the contents were shaken for 2 min. The two phases were allowed to separate and the absorbance of the separated chloroform layer was measured at 540 nm against a similar reagent blank. The coloured species were stable for 60 min. Drug concentration was computed from the calibration graph.

Pharmaceutical formulations :

Since only one formulation is available (Tablets), four different batches of this formulation were collected and analyzed as 4 sets to verify the proposed methods and the results were compared with the results of bulk drug. Accurately weighed quantity of tablet powder equivalent to 100 mg of drug was extracted with methanol (3 × 25.0 mL portions) and filtered. The volume of combined extract was brought to 100 mL with methanol to get stock solution (mg/ml). 50.0 ml of this stock solution (mg/ml) was taken and methanol portion was evaporated to dryness. After cooling, the residue was dissolved and diluted stepwise with the distilled water to obtain the working standard solution of, 500 µg mL⁻¹. The UV spectrophotometric method which was suggested for the identification of drug has been moulded for its assay and chosen as

the reference method for ascertaining the accuracy of the proposed method.

Results and discussion

Optimization of reaction conditions :

Optimum conditions for the proposed method were established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the colored species.

Optimum conditions :

The effects of various parameters such as buffer solution, concentration of the dye, organic solvent used for extraction, ratio of organic phase to aqueous phase during extraction, stability period and intensity of colored species were studied. The optimum conditions were as follows : 1.0–2.5 mL (0.55 – 1.4×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹) of Azocarmamine-G solution, 5.0–7.0 mL (5.0 – 7.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹) of buffer solution (pH 1.5), 1–5 min of shaking time and a laboratory temperature of (28 ± 2 °C) were found to be optimal. In the procedure, 2.0 mL of (1.1×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹) Azocarmamine-G, 6.0 mL (6.0×10^{-2} mol L⁻¹) buffer solution and 2 min shaking period required for maximum color development were found to be optimum conditions. Chloroform was preferred for its selective extraction of the complex from the aqueous phase. The ratio of aqueous to organic phase on extraction was taken as 3 : 2. The colored species were stable for 60 min. The λ_{\max} and ϵ_{\max} values were found to be 540 nm and 2.44×10^3 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ respectively (Table 1).

Mechanism of reaction :

In this method, the secondary amino group in between isopropyl and hetero cyclic moieties involves in ion-association complex with ACG. The proposed mechanism was given in Scheme.

Method of validation :

The developed method was validated as per ICH guidelines¹⁹ for its linearity, precision, accuracy, limit of detection and limit of quantification.

Regression analysis using the method of least square was made to evaluate the slope (*b*), intercept (*a*), and correlation coefficient (*R*) obtained from different con-

Table 1. Optimum conditions established for the proposed method

Parameter used for color development	Optimum range	Conditions in procedure	Remarks
λ_{\max} (nm)	545–550	540	–
Effect of buffer (Glycine-HCl buffer)	1.0–1.8	pH 1.5	Variations of pH of the buffer solution beyond the upper and lower limits resulted in low absorbance values
Volume of buffer solution	5.0–7.0 ml	6.0 ml	Variation of volume of buffer solution beyond the lower limit resulted in low absorbance values
Volume of ACG solution	1.0–2.5 ml	2.0 ml	2.0 ml of dye was necessary for covering the broad range of Beer's law limits
Choice of organic solvent	Chloroform	Chloroform	Other water immiscible solvents tested for the extraction of the coloured complex into organic phase include C_6H_5Cl , CCl_4 , <i>n</i> -butanol, C_6H_6 . $CHCl_3$ was preferred for its selectivity extraction of the complex from the aqueous phase
Ratio of aqueous to organic phase on extraction	3 : 2	3 : 2	The extraction of the coloured species into chloroform layer was incomplete when the ratio of aqueous to $CHCl_3$ phase was more than the specified ratio
Effect of shaking time	1–5 min	2 min	Constant absorbance values were obtained for the shaking period 1–5 min
Effect of temperature	$(28 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$	$(28 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C})$	At $< 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the extraction of the coloured species were found to be improper. At $> 35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ the stability of the coloured species was found to be less
Stability of colored species	1–60 min	5 min	The colored species were stable for 60 min, afterwards the absorbance gradually decreased

Scheme. Ion-association complex of AVS with ACG.

centrations of drug. The result of slope (3.65×10^{-3}) and intercept (1.2×10^{-3}) of drug by the proposed method was given in Table 2.

Linearity :

Linearity was found in the concentration range 50–150 mg mL^{-1} . Beer's law plots ($n = 6$) were linear with

Table 2. Regression parameters of proposed method

Regression equation ($Y = a + bC$) ^a	$Y = 0.00365C + 0.0012$
Slope (b)	3.65×10^{-3}
Standard deviation on slope (S_b)	7.66×10^{-6}
Intercept (a)	1.2×10^{-3}
Standard deviation on intercept (S_a)	8.12×10^{-4}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999

^a $Y = a + bC$ where C is the concentration of analyte in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and Y is the absorbance unit.

a correlation coefficient of 0.9999 (Table 2).

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) :

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were established according to ICH guidelines and determined by using the formula $\text{LOD} = K.SDa/b$ where $K = 3.3$ for LOD and 10 for LOQ. SDa is the standard deviation of the intercept and b is the slope of the calibra-

Table 3. Optical characteristics of the proposed method

λ_{max} (nm)	540
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	50–150
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	2.44×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g/cm}^2/0.001$ absorbance unit)	4.26×10^{-2}
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.3×10^{-1}
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.3×10^{-1}

tion line. LOD and LOQ were found to be as low as 7.3×10^{-1} and $2.3 \times 10^{-1} \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ respectively (Table 3).

Precision :

The repeatability of the proposed method was studied by repeating the method six times ($n = 6$). To study intra-day precision, the method was repeated six times a day. Similarly, the method was repeated on six consecutive days to determine inter-day precision (Table 4).

Table 4. Evaluation of precision and accuracy of proposed method

Precision (RSD) ^a	
Intra-day reproducibility (RSD, %)	0.77
Inter-day reproducibility (RSD, %)	0.64
% range of error ^b	
Confidence limit at 0.05 level (95%)	± 0.87
Confidence limit at 0.01 level (99%)	± 1.27

^aAverage of six determinations ($n = 6$). ^bAVS concentration : $10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$.

Accuracy :

The accuracy of the method was determined in terms of % recovery of AVS standard. Recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard drug solution at three different levels (8, 10, 12 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$) to previously analyzed sample (Tablet) solution. Values of recovery \pm SD were found to be in the range of $99.9 \pm 0.6 - 100.3 \pm 0.7$ ($n=3$) (Table 5).

Selectivity studies :

The extents of interference by various excipients that often accompany pharmaceutical formulations are tabulated in Table 6. To study the interference, 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of AVS was taken and a known amount of the interfering substance was added and the reaction was carried out as described under general procedure. The interference studies were carried out by repeating the method five times. The results showed the same absorbance as that of pure AVS. The high percentage of recovery showed that excipients did not interfere with the proposed method.

Application of the proposed method :

The application of the proposed method for the assay of pharmaceutical formulations was examined for tablets and the results were statistically compared with those

Table 5. Rrecovery studies by standard addition method

Proposed method	Formulation taken A ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Pure drug added B ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Total drug con. (A+B) ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	% Recovery ^a	
				\pm SD Lerka	\pm SD Lerez
ACG	10	8	18	100.2 ± 1.2	99.99 ± 0.6
"	10	10	20	99.9 ± 0.7	100.3 ± 0.7
"	10	12	22	100.1 ± 1.5	100.1 ± 0.2

^aAverage value of 3 determinations.

Table 6. Assay of AVS in the presence of excipients^a

Excipient	Concentration (mg mL ⁻¹)	Recovery (%) ^b
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3.0	99.9 ± 0.6
Magnesium stearate	4.0	99.8 ± 0.5
Microcrystalline cellulose	3.0	99.8 ± 0.2
Sodium starch glycolate	5.0	100.3 ± 0.4

^aConcentration of drug 50 µg mL⁻¹.
^bMean ±SD, n = 5.

instrument. In the present study Abacavir sulphate was determined successfully as pure compound as well as in formulations by exploiting specific functional group present. The proposed method is simple, rapid, sensitive, accurate and precise enough to be successfully adopted as an alternative method of HPLC technique for routine analysis and in pharmaceutical formulations without interference from excipients and additives.

Table 7. Assay of AVS in pharmaceutical formulations

Formulations	Labelled Amount (mg)	Amount found by proposed methods (mg) ^{a,b} ACG	Reference method ^c	% Recovery by proposed methods ^d ACG
Tablet Ziagen (Batch-I)	300	301.19 ± 1.83 <i>F</i> = 2.03 <i>t</i> = 2.1	298.13 ± 2.6	100.4 ± 0.61
Ziagen (Batch-II)	300	299.36 ± 1.87 <i>F</i> = 2.17 <i>t</i> = 0.21	299.9 ± 2.75	99.8 ± 0.62
Ziagen (Batch-III)	300	300.83 ± 0.83 <i>F</i> = 1.09 <i>t</i> = 2.2	298.65 ± 0.87	100.28 ± 0.28
Ziagen (Batch-IV)	300	301.84 ± 1.39 <i>F</i> = 1.65 <i>t</i> = 2.16	298.99 ± 1.09	100.61 ± 0.46

^aMean ±SD (n = 6). ^bTheoretical values of 95% confidence limit, *F* = 5.05, *t* = 2.57.

^cMean ±SD (n = 3). ^dAverage of three determinations (n = 3).

obtained by UV reference method. The results obtained by the proposed and UV reference method for the formulations were compared by means of Student's *t*-test and *F*-test and it was found that the proposed method do not differ significantly in precision and accuracy. The results are summarized in Table 7.

Conclusions

A significant advantage of visible spectrophotometric method is that it can be applied to the determination of individual compounds in a multicomponent mixture. The instrument is simple and is not of high cost. The importance lies in the chemical reactions upon which the procedures are based rather than upon the sophistication of the

Acknowledgements

One of the authors (TMS) is thankful to the Management of Gayatri Vidya Parishad College of Engineering, Visakhapatnam for providing facilities.

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